

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: FRANKLIN****FIRST NAME: DOH****PROGRAM CODE : DILT****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The Author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student used Turabian/Chicago footnote (Zotero) and confirmed below:

The Author used Zotero to insert references

The Author used Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 2%

The Author used Microsoft Word 365 on Windows 10

QUIZ FOR ACA-401D COURSE

1. What is research within the context of ACA-401D?

- Research is an organized and structured process intended at discovering new knowledge, understanding existing phenomena or solving specific problems.
- It is a careful planning, orderly data collection, and rigorous analysis to ensure the rationality and reliability of the findings.
- Research is the process to contribute to the body of knowledge in a particular field and to inform decision or action-based evidence.

- A process of systematic inquiry to answer a question that the researcher and others want to solve.¹**

2. **What are the steps to select a good research topic? Choose the correct Answer.**

- Carefully read and understand the guidelines provided for your research, scope, length and type of research.
- Consider choosing your research topic from an area that you are passionate about or curious to learn more about.
- Search your interests, make your topic manageable, question your topic, and evaluate your questions.²**
- Use academic databases, journals, books and sound websites to gather information and see what topic are broadly studied.

3. **According to Turabian Author Date Citation, what is the best citation style for single Author book?**

- Write the Author's last name first, followed by a comma, and then the first name.
- When citing the book in the text of your paper, include the author's last name and the year of publication
- Include the Author's first name, Last name, Date (in parentheses), Title, Editor(s)/Translator(s), Place, Publication Press.

¹ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago, United States of America: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 39.

² Turabian et al., 68.

Author's Last Name, Author's First Name. Year of Publication. Title of Book: Subtitle of Book. Place of Publication: Publisher's Name.³

4. Select the best answer. What are the factors that contribute to successful research?

Good communication, good planning, using an effective process for writing, attention to detail, openness to serendipity, visualizing success.⁴

Good reasons for choice of topic, methodology and analytical techniques.

Transparency, discussion with other researcher, typing speed.

All of the above.

5. **List the initial part of dissertation according to sequence?**

Title, dedication, biography, table of content, list of figures.

Title, dedication, abstract, table of content, supervisory committee.

Title, supervisory committee page, dedication, acknowledgement, table of content, list of tables, list of figures, biography and abstract.⁵

All of the above

6. **Choose the correct answer according to the text book. What is data Analysis?**

³ Turabian et al., 76.

⁴ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research. Second Edition* (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 42 – 48.

⁵ Sampson, 72 –76.

- Data analysis is the techniques that are used to answer research question or to test the hypothesis derived from the research question.⁶**
- Data analysis in research is the process of reviewing, organizing, and arranging data to help solve problems and answer questions.
- Data analysis is the method in which data is collected and organized so that one can derive helpful information.
- None of the above

7. **When is it appropriate to give credit**

- When one borrows up to three sentences from another source
- When another source is fully described during a research writing.
- When using any quote, paraphrase, statistics/data or visual such as graphs that is borrowed from another source.⁷**
- It is optional

8. **Which is the correct answer. What are the steps to follow after data collection?**

- Analyze the data collected from the participants
- Send aggregate summaries of the findings to participants who requested information.⁸**

⁶ Sampson, 66 – 69.

⁷ Laurent Cleenewerck and Gulma Kabiru, *ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK (PERIOD 1)* (Washington DC: Euclid University, 2024), 48 –52.

Provide an optional debriefing for the participants who want to learn about and discuss the aggregate results of the dissertation.

All of the above.

9. **Choose the correct Answer. The title of a research should contain one of the following.**

The title of the dissertation should indicate the variables, participants, and setting for the research.

The title of the dissertation should indicate the writer, meaning and setting for the research

The title of the dissertation should indicate the writer, setting of the research and method of data analysis.⁹

Month, Day, year.

10. **Acknowledgments most often include which of the following?**

Significant others who have provided support and encouragement to the student.

The major professor

Other faculty, administrators, and students who have provided support and encouragement.¹⁰

All of the above

⁹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, Fourth edition (Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019), 40 –46.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, 58 –62.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.